

THE EXTENT OF PERSONAL FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF PUBLIC AND PRIVATE HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS IN BACONG

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14203627>

ABSTRACT

This study aims to assess the financial practices of public and private high school teachers to gain insight about their financial behaviors. A descriptive research method was employed, involving 64 participants in Bacong. A tailored questionnaire was used that covered various financial aspects such as savings, spending, borrowing, and retirement planning. Data from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The results show that both public and private high school teachers engage in financial management, but differences exist. Private school teachers regularly save, while public school teachers prioritize saving for emergencies. In terms of spending, private school teachers focus on bill payments, while public school teachers aim to pay off debts promptly. Additionally, private school teachers are less inclined to take out loans for vehicles or properties compared to their public-school counterparts. Overall, both groups demonstrate similar approaches to financial management. Conclusions and recommendations are provided.

Keywords: *Saving, Spending, Borrowing, Retirement*

INTRODUCTION

Personal financial management has become increasingly important in today's world. This is because financial decisions are among the most important life shaping decisions that people make (Bosire et al., 2019). In recent decades financial products and services have

become increasingly widespread throughout society. Whereas earlier generations of Americans may have purchased goods primarily in cash, various credit products are popular today, such as credit and debit cards and electronic transfers (Federal Reserve Bank of San Francisco, 2022).

Today people are required to take increasing responsibility for managing a variety of risks over the life cycle. People who make sound financial decisions and who effectively interact with financial service providers are more likely to achieve their financial goals, edge against financial and economic risks, improved their household's welfare, and support economic growth (Ecija, 2022).

Teaching is not just a job; it is a calling. Teachers play an active role in shaping the character of a child and our future. It makes teaching a highly-respected profession across different segments of the human population throughout the world. For most teachers, the feeling of gratitude and achievement matters more than monetary gains. Such an attitude of compromise encourages policymakers to reduce the allocations for the education sector significantly. However, this is certainly not the case in the Philippines. Filipino teachers are overworked and underpaid, always getting the short end of the stick in terms of aid and support from the government. Their salaries are not on par with other professionals, and to make matters worse, they seldom receive their pay on time.

Teaching is a highly demanding profession. A teacher has to spend his time beyond his class hours for preparation and evaluation. It makes pursuing a second job for financial support practically impossible. It means a teacher has to meet all his financial obligations from his salary alone. Typically teachers manage their expenses through efficient fiscal discipline.

But when the certainty of salary on the set date is problematic, it makes their life quite miserable. To meet immediate financial requirements, they may resort to expensive loans such as payday loans, "5-6" loans, and ATM loans or cash loans that are just downright predatory. Such loans destabilize their financial strategies and force them to reel under a severe economic crisis.

Indebtedness among the public school teachers has long hunted the entire public school system in the Philippines. In 1991, the Congressional Commission on Education [EDCOM] survey recommended increasing the basic minimum wage salary of public teachers as part of the long needed educational reform. This recommendation was corollary to the findings that the teachers' salary in Manila alone highlighted the very low net salaries of teachers in the Philippines. Furthermore, almost one-fourth of the teachers (24%) lose half of their gross income to deductions for loan payments and a larger number of teachers (28%) get deductions amounting from 25% to 50% of their gross income (Ferrer, 2017).

Financial well-being is directly related to the overall satisfaction a person feels regarding his financial status. Financial wellness as an active state of financial health evidenced by

low debt level, active savings and/or retirement plan(s), and a good spending plan. 3 Low financial well-being or the presence of financial distress is shown to have detrimental effect on the psychological and physical health, reduce confidence and productivity in the workplace and increase absenteeism, delays, as well as lack of concentration. Debt is also seen as contributing to lower financial well-being and is identified as an “unfavorable financial condition” that causes financial stress (Ferrer, 2017).

The 1991 EDCOM survey and the Teacher Advancement for Optimum Well-being or the Project TAO Survey conducted by the Philippine Senate both recommended increasing the salary of teachers to uplift their financial capacity . Over the last decade, the teacher's salary has increased several times but it did not help the teachers improved their financial capability, too many, the increases still not enough for day-to-day expenses (Acedillo, 2018). As a matter of fact, Education Secretary Leonor Briones stated during her speech on Brigada Eskwela 2017 forum that it is very important that teachers should be financially literate because of the very reason that teachers' loan has been increasing throughout the years. She added that it is alarming because teachers indebted approximately Php 170 billion from private lending institution (Balanquit, 2020).

Being a public high school teacher, the researcher often face financial difficulties. There are also teachers who enter the profession with relatively low starting salaries, making it challenging to meet their financial needs. Hence, this paper aims to identify the underlying problems related to factors affecting personal financial management of public and private high school teachers. This study seeks to provide valuable insights that can be beneficial for various stakeholders, including educators, educational institutions, policymakers, and the broader community.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the public and private high school teachers in Bacong in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 marital status;
 - 1.4 no. of dependents;
 - 1.5 length of service; and
 - 1.6 highest educational attainment?
2. What is the extent of financial management practices of public high school in Bacong in terms of:
 - 2.1 saving;
 - 2.2 consumption;
 - 2.3 borrowing; and
 - 2.4 retirement?
3. What is the extent of financial management practices of private high school in Bacong in terms of:
 - 3.1 saving;
 - 3.2 consumption;
 - 3.3 borrowing; and

3.4 retirement?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the public-school respondents and their financial management practices?
5. Is there a significant relation between the profile of the private school respondents and their financial management practices?
6. Is there a significant difference between the financial management practices of public and private high school teachers?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Bacong, Negros Oriental. The town is a 4th class municipality in the province of Negros Oriental, Philippines. The researcher uses random sampling technique in data collection. To ensure representativeness in data, a total of 13 samples from the population of 27 were selected because the sample comprises 48% of the population of private schools. Representativeness is also observed in the samples from the public schools with 77% or 51 samples out of the 66 total population.

The researcher employed research self-made survey questionnaire in gathering the data. It aims to gather information that are necessary in determining the extent of financial management practices of the respondents. Pilot testing of the self-made survey questionnaires was conducted to fifteen (15) selected private high school teachers at Colegio de San Pedro Recoletos and fifteen (15) selected public high school teachers at Valencia National High School in Valencia to validate the instrument. The responses of 30 samples gave a Cronbach Alpha of 0.877, which means that responses are consistent between items or reliable, thus, internal consistency is good.

The statistical tool used in the study are frequency and percentage distribution, weighted mean to determine the extent of the respondents' financial management practices. Pearson R, Spearman Rank, and Eta-Squared Correlation were used to determine the relationship between the respondents' profile and financial management practices of public and private school teachers. Lastly, T-test was used to test the difference between the respondents' profile in terms of sex and their creativity indices in the five domains as per KDOCS. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

This study is focused on the personal financial management practices of both public and private high school teachers in Bacong, Negros Oriental. The teachers are classified as Junior High School and Senior High School teachers. The respondents will be coming from the three public high schools and two private high schools in Bacong, Negros Oriental, namely, a.) Buntod High School, b.) San Miguel National High School, and c.) Ong Che Tee Bacong High School for public high school and a) Bacong Holy Family High School and b) Divine Grace International Christian School for private high school. An approved letter of consent from the public schools district supervisor was given to the school heads of the three public high school and an approved letter of consent from the principal was given to the two private high schools prior to the conduct of the study.

RESULTS

1. Profile of the Respondents

1.1 Out of the 51 respondents from the public high school, 31.38% aged 31 – 40 years old, while out of 13 respondents from private, 69.23% aged 20 – 30 years old.

1.2 37 out 51 (72.55%) respondents are female in the public high schools, and 10 out 13 (76.92%) are also female in private high schools teachers.

1.3 As to civil status, most of the public high teachers are married (66.67%), while in private high school, most are single (69.23%).

1.4 In terms of number of dependents, both public and private high school teachers mostly have 1 – 3 dependents with a percentage of 52.94 and 69.23 respectively.

1.5 As to the length of service, private high school teachers majority have 0-5 years (61.54%) teaching experience, while public high school teachers are have been teaching 6 – 10 (41.18) and counting.

1.6 In terms of educational attainment, 10 out of 13 (76.93%) teachers in private are college graduates, while 32 out of 51 (62.75%) teachers in public schools are in the master's degree level.

2. The extent of personal financial management practices of public high school teachers

2.1 Public school teachers save primarily for emergency situations.

2.2 In terms of consumption, public teachers make sure to pay their debts in full on due dates, and then allocate for their monthly bills and expenses.

2.3 Borrowing is “moderately” practiced by public teachers to pay for emergency expenses and to construct/buy a house.

2.4 Public teachers' retirement plan prioritizes their possible health expenses.

3. The extent of personal financial management practices of private high school teachers

3.1 While saving for emergency ranked first, private teachers reported a “low” extent of practice in all saving factors.

3.2 Private teachers indicated that their salary is allocated first for their monthly bills and fixed expenses.

3.3 In terms of borrowing, private teachers indicated a “very low” extent of borrowing practice especially for less important things such as gadgets and vacation plans.

3.4 Majority of the respondents considered retirement plans putting possible health expenses first among other factors.

4. Relationship between Profile of Public School Teachers and their Financial Practices

4.1 Age is not significantly correlated with financial management practices.

4.2 Sex has moderate correlation with retirement.

4.3 Civil status has low correlation with savings.

- 4.4 Number of dependents is not significantly correlated with financial management practices.
 - 4.5 Length of service is not significantly correlated with financial management practices.
 - 4.6 Educational attainment is not significantly correlated with financial management practices.
 5. Relationship between Profile of Private School Teachers and their Financial Practices
 - 5.1 Age has high correlation with borrowing practices.
 - 5.2 Sex has low correlation with retirement.
 - 5.3 Civil Status has high correlation with borrowings.
 - 5.4 Number of dependents is not significantly correlated with financial management practices.
 - 5.5 Length of service has negative and moderate correlation with retirement.
 - 5.6 Educational attainment is not significantly correlated with financial management practices.
 6. The data revealed that both public and private school teachers are closely applying similar financial management practices.
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DISCUSSION

It is apparent that the majority of the private high school teachers are ages 20 to 30 years old. This indicates that majority of the private high school teachers are fresh graduates and are developing their teaching profession. This is coherent with what Salvan and Hambre (2020) point out that there is a rapidly growing number of young teachers, as might be expected from the large numbers participating in the Teacher Induction Scheme in the recent years.

Saving money for future needs and saving consistently and regularly are the top saving factors with an extent of practice of “moderate”. This contradicts the findings of Ferrer (2018) in his study on financial capability of public school teachers in the Philippines which demonstrated that only 23.2% of the teacher-respondents indicated that they save regularly, while 37.6% save money only sometime, 29.9% save for special occasion only.

The respondents demonstrate good financial management practices as 8 consumption factors out of 11 have a verbal description of “High”. Dalipe (2013) elucidated that teachers with less family responsibility and better career status have more favorable attitude while those with longer tenure have less favorable attitude. Respondents availed loans from GSIS, PAG-IBIG, banks, cooperatives, and even from other private lending agencies. Almost one-half of their gross income or around Php10,000.00 per month was used to pay their debts.

The finding of this study is promising as there is no borrowing factor with a “High” extent of practice. Clearly, applying loan for emergency purposes influences public high school teachers to borrow money. This finding also contradicts what Casingal (2021) found that

with the new normal teachers had to buy new laptops, tablets, smartphones, internet connectivity, and other devices for the online classes, which could be acquired through borrowing. Such borrowing factor in this study has a “Low” extent of practice.

The moderate extent of practice in all factors conveys that the respondents especially those who are nearing retirement are not just prioritizing or preparing for one aspect, but many such as for health which ranks first, potential investment, suitable lifestyles, and others. Magtira et al. (2021) explained that financial aspect is an aspiration that the participants have in mind regarding retirement, which can be achieved by being eligible to receive retirement pay from the academic institution they are associated with.

The results clearly show that the respondents from the private schools have a “low” extent of practice in all factors of savings. This can be attributed to the low to modest salary these respondents receive as most teachers in private high schools are not permanent teachers, hence the insufficient salary to be able to save. This finding contradicts Pinawin’s (2022) finding on his study about recreating financial literacy of private secondary school teachers wherein they were found to have “moderate” saving practices.

It is evident that spending fixed and prioritize expenses specifically on bills gains the top factor for private high school teachers as much as consumption is concerned. By prioritizing bills and expenses based on importance, one can meet essential needs, safeguard credit, and reduce financial stress. Consequently, one can concentrate on finding ways to reduce expenses or boost their income, enabling them to cover all monthly bills and potentially save for the future.

Interestingly, this is a promising result as private teachers have a “very low” extent of practice in terms of borrowing. With this, it can be surmised that even though private teachers do not receive high salaries, getting a loan to acquire a thing such as gadgets or pay bills is probably not their top option. There are several reasons why private high school teachers may be hesitant to borrow money. Though teaching is a noble profession, but it is often not known for providing high salaries especially in private schools. Many teachers face financial constraints due to relatively modest incomes. With limited discretionary income, taking on additional debt may be seen as a burden and can strain their monthly budgets. They may find it challenging to afford the monthly repayments and interest associated with a home loan, considering their salary. They may prefer to avoid taking on additional debt to maintain financial stability. This result supports what Mabignay et al. (2022) in his study that majority of the teachers borrowed money only once a year.

It is evident that possible health expenses is the topmost factor to consider when retiring. Teachers, like any other individuals, consider possible health expenses when retiring because healthcare costs can have a significant impact on their financial well-being. Healthcare costs have been steadily increasing over the years, and this trend is expected to continue. The cost of medical services, prescription medications, and long-term care can consume a significant portion of a retiree's budget. Teachers must anticipate these rising costs to ensure they have enough savings or other financial resources to cover their healthcare needs. This contradicts Damayon et al.’s (2022) study wherein the perceived

most important consideration for any preparation for retirement is financial which is followed by health considerations. It was further observed, however, that the physical-mental health concerns are intertwined with the financial or socio-economic status of retirees. Thus, financial preparation and cognitive or mental preparations for retirement are of paramount importance.

The Profile of Public School Teachers is not significantly correlated with financial management practices as demonstrated by the p-value of .655. This implies that the profile of the respondents has no effect with the financial management that the teachers are practicing and vice versa.

Generally, length of service is negatively and moderately correlated with financial management practices as demonstrated by the coefficient correlation of -.634, and such correlation is significant as exhibited by the p-value of .020. This implies that the former has a negative effect with the financial management that the teachers are practicing, and vice versa. Furthermore, the more length of service, the lesser frequency the financial management behaviors are practiced by the private school teachers and vice versa.

Conclusions

1. Public schools in Bacong have a considerable number of married female teachers who have more experience and background in handling their finances for their family. On the one hand, private schools in Bacong are also dominated by female teachers who are possibly fresh graduates and are still new to the teaching career and in handling finances.
2. Public school teachers appear to be underpaid, and their salary is barely enough to provide the needs of their family which makes saving a challenge for them to practice. These teachers are fully aware of what they are just capable of spending, so they try their best to avoid getting a loan if it is not necessary.
3. Saving is a big challenge for private teachers given the lower salary in private schools compared to what public school teachers receive generally, which can be attributed to the demands on consumption, which justifies their very low extent of practice in all of the borrowing factors.
4. The lack of correlation between the profile of the public school teachers and their financial management practices suggests that managing one's finances is a complex undertaking on a case-by-case basis.
5. In the case of private teachers, with an observed high correlation, their age and civil status are considered important determinants of their borrowing practices, while other aspects of their profile have lesser impact on the way they manage their finances.
6. Public school teachers have better financial practices as compared to private school teachers.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should receive training on creating comprehensive monthly budget plans and should participate in seminars on Employee Welfare and Benefits, particularly regarding loans. Additionally, they should undergo reorientation on the provisions outlined in the Code of Conduct of Professional Teachers emphasizing the importance of maintaining a positive reputation concerning financial matters including the repayment of debts and loans as well as the management of personal finances.
 2. The Department of Education should include in-service training for teachers on Money and Debt Management and raising awareness about lending agencies that can be beneficial for teachers as it enables them to formulate personalized spending and saving plans tailored to their specific situations, available resources, and financial goals.
 3. It is also recommended that the Schools Division of Negros Oriental in collaboration with the state universities actively engage in offering financial literacy sessions to teachers, equipping them with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively manage their finances. By tapping into the expertise and resources of the university, teachers can receive comprehensive training on budgeting, debt management, investment strategies, and other essential financial topics. This initiative would empower teachers to make informed financial decisions, improve their financial well-being, and positively impact their overall professional and personal lives.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

To address potential ethical issues, the researcher secured a permission from the school heads to conduct the study in the selected schools. Respondents were explicitly informed about the nature and purpose of the study. Considering the nature of their work, a schedule was arranged for the floating of the questionnaire. During the agreed schedule, it was emphasized that participation in the study is voluntary and they have the right to withdraw from the study any time. After retrieving the questionnaires, respondents were assured that their responses would only be used for research purposes only and would be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Acknowledgments

The successful completion of this study is attributed to the invaluable support and guidance of individuals who played significant roles in guiding the researcher. I am sincerely grateful to the following individuals and institutions for their contributions in broadening my perspectives throughout this study.

The researcher would like to express my sincere appreciation to my thesis adviser Dr. Heracelia Canoy, for her unwavering support, invaluable guidance, and insightful feedback. Her expertise in the field and her dedication to my academic growth have been instrumental in shaping the direction and quality of this research.

The researcher Joel P. Limson, Dr. Ildefe T. Villanueva, Dr. Jaysone Christopher M. Bancoro and Dr. Benjamin S. Villagonzalo Jr. for their valuable input, constructive criticism, and suggestions during the various stages of this study. Their expertise and scholarly insights have greatly contributed to the refinement and improvement of my research work.

The researcher extend my heartfelt gratitude to the faculty members of College of Business Administration, whose teachings, lectures, and mentorship have played a significant role in enhancing my understanding of the subject matter. Their passion for academia and their commitment to nurturing students' intellectual curiosity have been an inspiration to me throughout my academic journey.

The researcher would like to acknowledge the support and assistance provided by the staff and personnel of NORSU Main Graduate School, their prompt responses, administrative support, and provision of necessary resources have greatly facilitated the smooth progress of my research.

Furthermore, The researcher would like to express my appreciation to the participants of this study, Colegio de San Pedro Recoletos, Valencia National High School, Buntod High School, San Miguel National High School, Ong Che Tee – Bacong High School, Bacong Holy Family High School, and Divine Grace International Christian School whose willingness to share their time, experiences, and perspectives have enriched the findings and outcomes of this research. Their contributions are invaluable, and I am grateful for their involvement.

Lastly, The researcher would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to my family and friends for their unwavering love, encouragement, and understanding throughout this study. Their constant support, patience, and belief in my abilities have motivated me to overcome challenges and persevere in my academic pursuits.

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